

HISTORY OF THE ORIGIN OF THE FOOTBALL GAME

Nuriddinov B.

Karshi State University, Teacher of the Department of Physical Education and Sports, Faculty of Sports

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Abstract. *Football is the most popular team game in the world, where you have to fight for even the smallest points. Until now, many people think that the homeland of football is England, but this is not the right idea. More precisely, it is a very wrong idea. In fact, the history of "football" spans several hundred years and covers many countries.*

Keywords: *football, history, ancient football, Roman football, medieval football.*

INTRODUCTION

Football has reached the peak of its popularity in Europe, South America, Latin America, Africa and partly in Asia. In many countries, football is considered a part of the culture of these countries, and as an object of national opinion, it shows the great attention paid to football all over the world.

Today, football is the most important sport in the world. In the second half of the 20th century, with the participation of national teams in various tournaments, the popularity of club teams in international competitions increased. The development of women's football is also visible. In many countries, "mini-football", "beach football" and various types of football are being developed and culturalized.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY.

The oldest source is the annals of the Han Dynasty, which ruled ancient China. These chronicles have a history of 2000 years. A game played similar to kicking a ball is Tsu-Chu (which originated in ancient China around 250 BC). "Tsu" means kicking the ball with the foot, and "Chu" means "inflated leather ball". According to the chronicles, this game was played in honor of the emperor's birthday. In the game "Tsu Chu" it was required to enter the ball into a small slot, that is, into the goal. As a gate, bamboo sticks were placed in a vertical position, and the opening was 30-40 centimeters in diameter and 9 meters high. As you can see, to play this game one needs to have a certain skill [1].

The period between the 20th and 16th centuries was the golden age of the Kemari game. The game was also popular among ordinary people, and this game encouraged poets and writers to create. According to Japanese chronicles, an emperor and his team kept the ball in the air with a thousand hits and the ball was hidden after the game. From the 13th-14th centuries, special clothes were used for the game "Kemari". "Kemari" players wore long-sleeved clothes. Even now, there are people who play "Kemari" in Japan. This game was mainly played by enthusiasts who wanted to preserve their traditions[2].

The history of ball games in Central America dates back to 1600 BC and that game is Pok-A-Tok. that is, it was called ("Paso de la Amada"). The playing fields at Paso de la Amada have expanded and improved over 150 years.

It turns out that the North American Indians also had a foot-kicking game called pasuckuakohowog, which is translated as "they came together to play ball with their voices". The

games were held at the beginning of the 17th century and were held at gates 1 km wide, 2 km apart. Up to 1,000 people participated in the game "Rasuckuakohowog" [3].

In Australia, the rules and regulations of the football games played there have not reached us.

In ancient Egypt, ball games existed much earlier than in other countries. That is, the "artifacts" found in Egypt not earlier than 2500 years BC indicate that there was a game similar to football in Egypt at that time[4].

Playing ball games in ancient Greece dates back to at least the 4th century BC. According to legend, the goddess Aphrodite gave the first ball to Eros, saying: "I will give you a wonderful toy, this is a speeding ball, you won't find a better one even in Hephes". Depending on the target, the ball could be compared to the Sun, Moon and Earth[5].

They can be found and encountered in the sources of ancient Chinese and Japanese writings. "Football plots" were found on the bas-reliefs of ancient Egyptian pharaohs and ancient Greeks. These games were not only entertaining games, but also provided physical training of the military. Historians have compared the soccer ball to the sun based on the assumption that the ancient football originated from the language (the sun warms everyone - and football unites everyone)[6].

Roman football - harpastum. The Greek game of Episkyros was later adopted by the Romans and they called the game of Episkyros the game of Harpastum. The rules of the game "Episkiros" were also slightly changed and it was used for the game "Harpastum". "Harpastum" (in translation - a game with a small ball) was popular among people for 700 years. They mostly played with a small but heavy ball. In this game, it was necessary to pass the ball between two sticks, and this game was used to practice the varsity. From 5 to 12 players from both teams participated in the game. The games were played on a rectangular field divided into two equal parts. The members of each team had to keep the ball as long as possible, and the opposing players had to bring the ball into their field. The game was distinguished by its brutality. "The players were divided into two teams, the ball was placed on the line in the center of the field. The line was drawn in front of each player, and the task of both teams was to bring the ball inside the drawn line, and the ball was to be pushed to the side by the player of the opposing team. According to the ancient Roman contemporaries, the definition given above is the definition given to gaspartum, which reminds football[7-9].

After the collapse of the Roman Empire, "Harpastum" was preserved under different names in the countries that emerged in its place: "Pa sup" in France, and "Calcio" in Italy. The game played with a ball - Calchio (Florence) appeared in Italy around the 16th century. In Florence, this game is considered the cradle of the Pizzeria della Novera. Over time, the game became known as "giuoco del Calcio fiorentino" (Fiorentina foot game) or simply "Calco". The official rules of Calcho were published by Giovanni Bardi in 1580. Like the Roman game of Harpastum, Calcho was played with both hands and feet, and the number of players was 27. A goal is written for the team that took the ball from the designated point on the field. In the beginning, "Kalcho" was mainly a game for the upper classes and was mainly played on the eve of religious holidays. Even Vatican Popes Clement VII, Leo IX and Urban VIII themselves played Calcho[10].

RESULTS. If we take a look at the history of football in our country using the analysis of the above literature, modern football appeared in Uzbekistan at the beginning of the last century and quickly became a popular game. The places of its development were Fergana, Tashkent,

Andijan, Kokand and Samarkand. For the first time football played in Fergana. In the same place, at the end of 1911, the first football team was formed. In August 1912, the number of football teams formed in Ferghana allowed to unite into "Football team".

After a while, they started playing football in Tashkent. Among football fans from Tashkent, the most famous team was TOJIC - "Tashkentskoe obshestvo lyubiteley sporta" (TSIJ - Society of Tashkent sports fans). This society was established in 1912, and in a very short time, it served a lot for the development of football and other sports. In the second half of 1912, the game of football began to spread in Uzbekistan. Interest in the game of football has also increased in Kokand, Andijan and Samarkand. The most interesting stage of these years was definitely the meeting of Fergana, Tashkent, Andijan, Samarkand players. The first players who visited Tashkent were members of Samarkand Footballers' Club (SFT). Summing up the initial period of football development in Uzbekistan, it is worth mentioning that despite the lack of football fields and training sessions, in a short time talented players from Fergana, Tashkent, Kokand, Andijan and Samarkand who made a great contribution to the development of Uzbek football appeared. It should be mentioned here that, despite the successful spread of football not only in Fergana, Tashkent and Samarkand, but also in other cities of Uzbekistan, its development was slow. There was no team training system, training was very simple and was held from time to time. No official competition was held in Tashkent. Since 1920, football has penetrated into remote villages and makhallas of our republic and has become a popular game. Young people, students, workers and farmers began to play football. The year 1921 is significant as the first match between Moscow and Tashkent football players was held. In 1925, the country's Council of Physical Education created a calendar of public physical activities. The organization of football in Uzbekistan began to have a slightly more organized system. Thus, Tashkent Championship was held in 3 categories and 28 teams took part in it. In 1927, the All-Uzbek Spartakiad, which was an important stage in the training of Uzbek athletes, was held. In the Spartakiad final, the teams of Tashkent and Fergana, who were permanent rivals, met. Members of the national team of Uzbekistan performed in both teams. Participation in the international Spartakiad held in Moscow in 1928 was an extremely serious test for the players of Uzbekistan. 22 teams competed for the first place in football spartacia, among them there were the national teams of working clubs of England, Germany, Australia, Switzerland and Finland. The meeting between the teams of Switzerland and Uzbekistan attracted great interest among football fans. Uzbek players showed team play, beautiful and agile combinations in this game.

Starting from 1937, on the basis of football competitions, not the matches of the national teams of the city, but the competitions of club teams for the Cup of Uzbekistan and the championship began to be held. In 1939, the performance of Tashkent dynamists in the fight for the former Union Cup was a great success. On August 28, at the "Dynamo" stadium in Moscow, Uzbek players played against the "Temp" team of Baku in the quarter finals. Tashkent players seriously prepared for the football season of 1941. According to the schedule of the championship matches, they should have hosted the Alma-Atalik club. On June 22, 1941, the Great Patriotic War began, and the sports life of Uzbekistan was temporarily suspended.

From 1960 to 1991 (with breaks), "Pakhtakor" participated in the higher league of the former Union. It was a period of reforms and fundamental changes. Only after the qualifying matches in small groups, they went to the championship. The team preparing for the High League was formed on the basis of two teams from Tashkent, "Pakhtakor" and "Mehnat Zahiralari" clubs.

DISCUSSION.

In 1994, the ambassadors of the young independent republic were introduced for the first time at the 12th Asian Games held in Japan - a major sports forum in the Asian region. In the fight for the title of gold medalists, Uzbek players won over the national teams of Saudi Arabia (4:1), Malaysia (5:0), Hong Kong (1:0) and Thailand (5:4). In the quarter-finals, they defeated the national team of Turkmenistan with a score of 3:0, and in the intense and very complicated game of the semi-finals, they defeated the strong team of South Korea with a score of 1:0. And, in the final, they defeated the Chinese national team with a score of 4:2. The coaches of this team were associate professor R.Akramov and sports master B.Abduraimov. It is worth mentioning that 7 players of the main team were students of UzDJTI[11].

CONCLUSION. The first game that is similar to football and has scientific evidence is juju, a sport played for military training in China between 300 and 200 BC. The goal of this game was to move a ball of leather filled with wool, fixed with two bamboo canes, into a castle 30-40 cm high; the ball could be touched by any part of the body except hands and arms. A few centuries later, a game called kemari appeared in Japan, which also has traces of juju, dating back to 644 AD. Unlike cuju, the goal of non-competitive kemara was based on players hitting the ball with their feet on a circular field and passing the ball to each other without dropping it. The first football-like game in Europe was a game called episkyros, played in Ancient Greece. In a free contact game with every part of the body, players were divided into two teams and each team tried to pass or shoot the ball over the line at the end of the opposing team's field. A similar game was later played in the Roman Empire under the name harpastum.[12]

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